

Preferred Choice of Teaching Methodology - Teacher Centered or Student Centered?

IZAM AFZAL¹, ANSAR LATIF², AYESHA ZAHEER³, ANILA ANSAR⁴, NAMRA CHAUDHARY⁵, SHER AFGHAN⁶

ABSTRACT

Aim: To statistically analyse the factors involved in popularity of both the teaching methods being practiced in medical colleges.

Study design: Questionnaire based study.

Place & duration of study: Department of General Surgery and Medical Education, Khawaja Muhammad Safdar Medical College, Sialkot from November 2017 to May 2018.

Methods: Two categories for comments Group I - Teacher centered Teaching and Group II- Student centered Teaching (Modern) were made and results compiled. The questionnaire was to be filled completely and a time of 6 months was given to answer all questions. The respondents were supposed to comment on both systems upon each and every point they raised. The collected questionnaires were studied and any queries and ambiguities were made clear by talking to the doctors in person or on telephone. Those who incompletely filled the questionnaires were excluded from the study. Data was entered and analysis done by SPSS v 22.

Results: One thousand students included in study were of public sector and private sector and 175 teachers. Group-I of Teacher centered Teaching & Group-II of Student centered Teaching (Modern) methods, In group-I comments, Teachers were 81% dominated, 90% teachers were interested & 55% were not interested, 35% had problems with the classroom 70% had problems with the technology used, attendance of the students was 29% while regularity of teachers was 89% & syllabus coverage was 75%, 20% were having problems with the practical sessions, lack of teaching skills was in 35% & 60% gave inappropriate time to all students. In group-II comments, Teachers were 19% dominated, 10% teachers were interested & 45% were not interested, 89% had problems with the classroom 30% had problems with the technology used, attendance of the students was 71% while regularity of teachers was 100% & syllabus coverage was 40%, 70% were having problems with the practical sessions, lack of teaching skills was in 45% & 20% gave inappropriate time to all students.

Conclusion: Though there are numerous advantages being observed in modern teaching but the time tested traditional teaching has an impact of being sure method of covering syllabus as well as personal interaction of students and teachers and the assessments are more reliable.

Key words: Postgraduation, public sector, private sector. Traditional, Modern

INTRODUCTION

From centuries, tutors have been using different methods of teaching some of those remained in use for years & have become the traditional methods of education like textbooks study and lecture-based classes. Traditional approaches are mostly teacher-centred¹.

But now-a-days, many new methodologies are gaining popularity among learners and students due to increasing advances in information technologies and internet. Some of these new approaches include computers, multimedia, online courses, problem based or student-centred education, interactive sessions etc. It is seen that almost all of these categories have their advantages and disadvantages².

Computer helps in making study interesting & knowledgeable, students can work independently on it. Moreover, video and audio based educational approaches

increase learning and absorption. Use of Multimedia and projectors in classrooms and different conferences lessens the need for board writing, projectors and wall charts³.

Various online courses from anywhere in the world provide a fast and feasible approach to many students for increasing their capabilities and skills⁴. Computers can never replace a good mentor, who always has a big role in personality and character building of the students and making them good human beings⁵.

Problem based learning which is also called student oriented learning is one of the important methods of modern age. It was first started in Ontario, Canada on McMaster's Medical University by Howard Barrows. It is gaining popularity among students but a teacher has to do much work to implement this method in routine^{6,7}.

Traditional teacher-centred technique is unique in having the role of tutor in the provision of proper guidance and supervision, the opinions of teachers on the basis of their own experiences in their fields of education are such noble things which no multimedia or computer can provide to the students⁸.

Other methods which use both traditional and innovative approaches are mind maps, mnemonic words, use of humor, sense while teaching. Combination of both traditional and newer techniques of education should be used for the best results in aspect of students learning & cognition improvement^{9,10}. No study has been

^{1,5,6}HO Surgery, Kh Muhammad Safdar Medical College, Sialkot.

²Associate Professor Surgery, Allama Iqbal Memorial Teaching Hospital, Sialkot.

³Assistant Professor Physiology, Khawaja Muhammad Safdar Medical College, Sialkot.

⁴Associate Professor Gynaecology and Obstetrics, Khawaja Muhammad Safdar Medical College, Sialkot.

⁶SMO, Tehsil Head quarter Hospital, Daska

Correspondence TO Dr Izam Afzal, Email: izamafzal6@gmail.com, Cell: +923455927009.

conducted on this issue so far in our college and colleges of District Sialkot ; so we wanted to carry out this project.

SUBJECTS AND METHODS

Questionnaires were distributed to students of all academic years of MBBS degree course in three medical colleges. Similarly interviews and questionnaire based views were sought from senior as well as junior doctors working on teaching appointments of public and private sector medical colleges of district Sialkot of Pakistan. Two categories for comments Group I Teacher centered Teaching (Traditional) and Group II- Student centered Teaching (Modern) were made and results compiled. The questionnaire was to be filled completely and a time of 6 months was given to answer all questions. The respondents were supposed to comment on both systems upon each and every point they raised. The collected questionnaires were studied and any queries and ambiguities were made clear by talking to the doctors in person or on telephone. Those who incompletely filled the questionnaires were excluded from the study. Data was entered and analysis done by SPSS v 22.

RESULTS

General variables in the study are depicted in Table I. Table II shows feedbacks expressed in terms of percentages. These factors were having a negative shade or feature; however definite good or bad comments cannot be labeled. Table III: Final remarks of the groups

Table I: Study to summarize

Total Students in study	1000
Public sector students	625
Private sector students	375
Senior faculty	93
Junior faculty	82
Faculty from Pre clinical subjects	67
Faculty from clinical subjects	108

Table II: Findings of the Questionnaires/ comments

	Total subjects	1175(100%)
	Group I-	Group II-
Teachers' dominate	951 (81%)	223(19%)
Interest of teachers	1057 (90%)	117(10%)
Uninteresting Content	646 (55%)	528(45%)
Problems with the classrooms	411(35%)	1045(89%)
Problems with the technology used	822(70%)	352(30%)
Attendance of the students	340(29%)	834(71%)
Regularity of teachers	1045(89%)	1175(100%)
Syllabus coverage	881(75%)	470(40%)
Problems with the practical sessions	235(20%)	822(70%)
Lack of teaching skills	411(35%)	528(45%)
Inappropriate attention/time to all students	705(60%)	235(20%)
Interaction of students and teachers	888	287

Table: III Conclusion

	Teacher centered Teaching	Student centered Teaching	Inconclusive
Private sector students	37%	23%	40%
Public sector students	55%	39%	6%
Private sector teachers	65%	32%	3%
Public sector teachers	58%	32%	10%

DISCUSSION

The approach is more close to old-style apprenticeship learning. The experience teaching large lecture classes has been declared to be quite good by the teachers. The medical teachers of public sector was a bit more inconclusive while private sector teachers.

Inappropriate time and unequal attention to different students was the main drawback in traditional teaching while, lack of attention and interest by the teachers in assignments done by students in modern internet based work was the leading objection.

Time consumption and uncertainty of covering the syllabus was a hinderance superadded by the deficiency of faculty in modern teaching. This factor was more marked in private sector medical colleges. Moreover lack of teaching skills and inexperience of medical teachers was a complaint by the private sector students.

Traditional teaching have inbuilt error of being inadequate and boring; while modern tools is good but more student dependant.

Our study showed that 37% of private sector students liked traditional teaching & 23% considered modern teaching methods more good, but 40% of them remained inconclusive while study by Connell et al¹¹ showed them to be 32%,27% & 38% respectively.

We reported the incidence of preferring traditional teaching in 55% & modern teaching in 45% of public sector students, of which 6% were inconclusive, while the data of Evmenova et al¹² showed this incidence to be 52%, 47% & 4% respectively.

According to our data,65% of Private sector teachers were using traditional teaching methods & 32% used modern methodology, but 3% remained inconclusive about their preference, while the study of Mahira et al¹³ reported the percentages of 66%, 27% & 1% respectively.

About 58% of Public sector teachers used the approaches of traditional teaching in our research, and 32% were on the side of modern methods,10% of public sector teachers also remained inconclusive, while the study of Akbulut et al¹⁴ showed them to be respectively.

CONCLUSION

Though there are numerous advantages being observed in modern teaching but the time tested traditional teaching has an impact of being sure method of covering syllabus as well as personal interaction of students and teachers and the assessments are more reliable.

Conflict of interests: No conflict of interests

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